

ECO-FRIENDLY STATUS, RELIGIOUS DISTINCTION, AND SOCIO-CULTURAL SIGNIFICANCE OF BINSAR MAHADEV SHRINE 'MAHADEV OF DUDHATOLI' Dr. Pankaj Priyadarshi**

ABSTRACT

The subject of the present study is the hieratic shrine, **Binsar Mahadev**, situated in the Dudhatoli landscape of Uttarakhand. This mythological Shiva temple is ascertained in the middle of the rich temperate forest region of the Central Himalayas. The temple falls in the Pauri Garhwal district at Thalissain, Patti Chauthan. Its architecture is similar to Katyur's style. Idols of Lord Hargauri, Ganesh, Mahishasur Mardini, Lakshmi-Narayana, Shiva family, breastfeeding Kartikaiya, booted Surya, Anantanaga, Hanuman, brothers of Binsar Mahadev - Heet and Ghantakarna, Sahastra Linga, etc. are seated in the temple, with many mythological symbols. In this holy temple, the entire Devasthan is worshipped instead of any particular idol. There are also other religious places around the temple such as Chhachori (the court of Devsabha), Brahmadhungi, and the small temple of Bhagawati/Deeva Mata. Due to the dilapidation of the temple, a restoration program is launched by BKTC (Badrinath Kedarnath Temple Committee). After the renovation, the temple would include the four Dhams of Uttarakhand. The study aims to highlight the facts related to the temple and the Dudhatoli landscape, as well as to relate Mahadev Shiva as an ecologist of Dudhatoli.

Keywords : Dudhatoli landscape, Binsar Mahadev, Brahmadhungi, Shiva as an ecologist.

Dudhatoli : An Introduction

The holy temple, **Binsar Mahadev** falls in the Dudhatoli landscape in Lesser Himalaya. It is stretched in the Chamoli, Pauri Garhwal, and partially in the Almora district of Uttarakhand. The region is situated in the south of Main Central Thrust, and north of North Almora Thrust (Joshi, et al., 2016). Two major tectonic features are controlling the litho-stratigraphy and morphology of the zone (Goswami & Pant, 2008). It forms an elevated plateau with the highest altitude reaching more than 3114 meters above mean sea level. The mountain range is

located between the latitudes 30° 0.993' to 30° 03.764' N and longitudes 79° 09.724' to 79° 12.040' E, covering an area of 3,843 h. and 493 km² (Chauniyal & Dutta, 2018). Climatologically the region falls in Sub-Alpine to Moist Alpine (Jayal T. , 2014) in the north with distinguished forest types. It originates five rivers of environmental importance named Western Ramganga, Vino/Vinod, Atagad, Eastern Nayar, and Western Nayar (Jayal & Chuniyal, 2015). Along with this, Dudhatoli is the breeding ground of many birds, and animals and also the mother of various species of medicinal plants and timber (Table 1).

Table 1. List of various plants including medicinal plants and timber in the Dudhatoli landscape.

Vernacular Name	Scientific Name	Life Form	Uses
Burans	Rhododendron arboretum	Tree	Timber/Medicinal
Deodar	Cedrus deodara	Tree	Timber/Medicinal

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Silver Fir	<i>Abies alba</i>	Tree	Timber
Spruce	<i>Picea</i>	Tree	Timber
Timoor	<i>Zanthoxylum armatum</i>	Shrub	Medicinal
Kilmora	<i>Berberis asiatica</i>	Herb	Medicinal
Utees	<i>Alnus nepalensis</i>	Tree	Medicinal/firewood
Banj	<i>Quercus leucotrichophora</i>	Tree	Timber
Kharsu	<i>Quercus semecarpifolia</i>	Tree	Timber
Ratanjot	<i>Geranium wallichianum</i>	Herb	Medicinal
Akhrot	<i>Juglans regia</i>	Tree	Timber/Medicinal
Neelkanthi	<i>Ajuga parviflora benth</i>	Herb	Medicinal
Kaphal	<i>Myrica esculenta</i>	Tree	Medicinal
Dev Ringal	<i>Thamnocalamusfalconeri</i>	Grass	Handicraft
Chir	<i>Pinus roxburghii</i>	Tree	Timber

Source: Adapted from(Sharma, Butola, Ghildiyal, & Gairola, 2013).

In July 2014, the construction work of the assembly building of Uttarakhand started at Bharadisain in the Gairsain block of Chamoli District. On March 4, 2020, Chief Minister Trivendra Singh Rawat declared it the summer capital of Uttarakhand (Mittal, 2020). According to Hem Gairola, a person well-versed with Van Panchayat, in 1912, the Forest Department issued a title list, and herders of this region were allotted land for making temporary cattle shelters for seasonal grazing in the pasture locally known as Kharak. 99 Kharaks of 800 breeders are currently present in Dudhatoli. The thick, luscious and juicy grass of this landscape produces plenty of good quality milk. This gave the region its name Dudhatoli '**Doodh-ki-Tauli**' (*Cauldron of milk*).

Objectives of the Study

The chief objective of the present research paper is to bring light to the facts based on historical, archaeological, environmental, religious, cultural, and folk beliefs related to the Dudhatoli landscape, especially the mythological shrine Binsar Mahadev. It analyzes the known facts and conducts its critical study based on new knowledge.

Material and Methods

Study Area (figure: 1)

The geographical location of Binsar Mahadev temple is between 30°0'59.51" north latitude and 70°9'43.58" east longitude. The height of the temple is about 2821 meters(Jha, 1996) above mean sea level.

There are two routes to reach the Binsar Mahadev temple. The first one passes through the Thalısain block of Pauri Garhwal district. The second route passes through Deghat from Jainal in Almora district on 'State Route Number 12' or 'Bhatraujkhan-Ganai-Chaukhutia road. Both the routes are covered with rich evergreen forests.

Figure:1 Map of the study area.

Source: Adapted from (Kala, Bhavsar, Kumar, Roy, & Rawat, 2018).

The present research article is based on both primary and secondary data. Secondary data has been compiled through related literature, thesis, research papers, websites, etc. The researcher anthologized the primary data with a survey of various historical sites of Binsar Mahadev temple and Dudhatoli landscape and

interviews with concerned persons of the region. Appropriate use of historical analysis and exploratory methods are used to evaluate the data, material, and information received.

Field Notes

Binsar Mahadev (Cauhana) or Bindeshwar Mahadev temple is one of the ancient holy temples of Uttarakhand (figure:2). It provides blissful peace in the captivating shade of nature. Temple is located in a dense

Figure:2 Binsar Mahadev temple.

There are three huge stone idols of Ganesha around the Shrine (figure:4). A mythological Shivaling is also at the pylon. According to Babaji, every time Shivaling surfaces during digging around the temple, even after many years. Many idols in a dilapidated state are re-positied in the temple complex. It is believed all these idols are set to be ruined when the Gorkha kings of Nepal invaded Garhwal.

Figure 4 : The idol of Ganesha before the pylon.

forest area covered by more than a hundred years old deodar trees. There is a huge stone idol of Ganesha before the entrance of the temple on the right side. Devotees enter the temple after walking a little further on the right from the main gate is the entrance to the ancient shrine. There is an indecipherable petrograph on the same wall. It is the local belief that it was written by Vishwakarma (figure:3).

Figure : 3 Inscription by Vishwakarma.

Lord Hargauri, Ganesha, Mahishasur Mardini, Lakshmi-Narayana, Shiva family, breastfeeding Kartikaiya, booted Surya, Anantanaga, Hanuman, brothers of Bindeshwar Mahadev - Heet and Ghantakarna (Maithani, 2004), and many other idols are seated in the womb chamber. A '**Sahasra Linga**' is also seated at Binsar Mahadev, received similar from sites such as Jageshwar, Bageshwar, Baijnath, Khunt, and others (Joshi M. M., 2017). There is a small hermitage on the right side of the shrine, in which the sages and saints reside. Presently, saint Shree Sitaram Babaji has been practicing meditation here since 2016. There exists a Dharmshala at a distance of about 100 meters from the temple, which has been built for the night stay of the devotees and visitors.

In the temple courtyard, three streams flow inside a mythical bathhouse. These streams get out from inside three beautiful sculptures of lion faces. It is assumed that

there was a pool of cold water under the main temple in ancient times. It has been covered now. According to a local belief, 2 Km away from the temple complex, the water of the pool originates in a spring near the village Sundergaon. The getting of rice and other grains that have fallen in the pool, at this place reveals the truth of this fact.

Every year on the Ekadashi that falls after Diwali a fair begins with a grand Jatra in this temple. On the occasion of the annual fair, the devotees donate the bull (Nandi). Childless women execute "Thad Dee" (*Standing in water all night with a burning lamp in hand*) at night. In the morning, after the ablution of **Pooranmasi Snan**, all the devotees go back to their homes.

There are many legends associated with the construction of this temple such as Vishwakarma built the temple, in due course of their exile the Pandavas built the temple in one night and established Bhairavanath here, the temple was built by Maharaja Prithvi in the 9th or 10th century in memory of his father Maharaja Bindu. Hence, the temple is also known as Bindeshwar, etc. The whole shrine is constructed with stone apart from a wooden canopy. It is a beautiful example of Pagoda elegance. Its architecture is similar to the Katyuri style. Babaji apprised the fact that many times the shrine has been inspected by the Archaeological Department, but no accurate particulars acknowledged about the fabrication of the temple.

Binsar Mahadev is an incarnation of Lord Shiva. The main idol is headless hence the temple's name is Binsar Mahadev. In the local parlance, Binsar derives its name from Binsar Bela (*Brahma Muhurta*). A mythical platform built on a mound about half a kilometer from the temple is called Chhachori, the "Court of Dev Sabha" used to be held in this complex in ancient times. Above the village of Daida, a giant rock named Brahmadhungi is

found which is 460 meters in circumference. There is also a small shrine of Deeva Mata on it. It is believed that the Pandavas constructed the Binsar Mahadev temple in one night. Bhima was entrusted with the responsibility of collecting the rock for construction. In the last quarter of the night started, he left this rock here, since then this rock been here. According to another folktale, Brahma himself placed this rock here, hence this place started to be called Brahmadhungi.

Babaji told that Brahmadhungi is where the first and last rays of sunrise and sunset fall. The main Dudhatoli mountain is at a distance of 12 km from here. When the weather is clear, the eastern Himalayas of Garhwal, the western Himalayas of Nepal, the entire Chauthan belt, and some parts of the Lohba belt, Chandpur belt, Badhan belt, and Ranikhet are visible from here. Kodiabagarh, the Samadhi of Veer Chandra Singh Garhwali, is near Bindeshwar Mahadev. On June 12, a cultural fair is held here in his memory every year.

Mahadev of Dudhatoli, as an Ecologist of the region

The author observes that due to the temple of Lord Shiva, the plethora of biodiversity is conserved in and around the temple complex. Summarizing all the legends, one can say that Lord Shiva in a true sense is a conservationist. In 2016, 3rd-7th January, the **103rd Indian Science Congress** was held in Karnataka at the University of Mysore. The chairman of MP PURC, AK. Pandey presented a paper entitled **Lord Shiva as a great environmentalist in the world**. In this paper, he reveals Shiva as the most eco-friendly person to have incarnated on earth (Sengupta, 2019). The nature of Shiva and the methods of His worship described in ancient texts encourage environmental protection and promotion of biodiversity (Mishra & Rout, 2020)

Table: 2 Natural resources and products related to Shiva.

Vernacular Name	Botanical Name	Uses	Life Form
Kailash Parvat	-	Abode of Shiva	Mountain
Ganga	-	Ornament	Water
Vasuki Naag	-	Ornament	Reptile
Ardh Chandra	-	Ornament	Moon of the earth

Rudraksha	Elaeocarpus ganitrus	Ornament	Tree
Nandi	Bos taurus	Vehicle of Shiva	Animal
Bhang	Cannabis sativa	Rituals	Herb
Dhatura	Datura stramonium	Rituals	Herb
Bilwa	Aegle marmelos	Rituals	Tree
Chandan	Santalum album	Rituals	Tree
Arka	Calotropis gigantea	Rituals	Shrub
Doorva	Cynodondactylon	Rituals	Grass
Kesar	Crocus sativus	Rituals	Perennial plant
Shahad	-	Rituals	Bee product
Badri	Zizyphusmauritianana	Rituals	Shrub or thorny tree
Dugdha	-	Rituals	Animal product

Whither Shiva's love for flora and fauna creates a sense of entity, on the other side, the tiger's blister and pyre ash draped over the body symbolize mortality. Thus, Shiva concatenates human beings to become ecologically susceptible.

Conclusion

The origin of five rivers and various species of flora and fauna make the Dudhatoli landscape environmentally important. It would be more appropriate to call the Dudhatoli landscape a zone of abundant ecological diversity than the Pamir. There are many scenic religious places around Binsar Mahadev and Dudhatoli landscape. Despite it, this place is not much developed. The roads leading to the temple should be made easy without harming nature. Rest houses and refreshments should be arranged on the pedestrian route. This will make such a long journey easier for the devotees and visitors. Dharmshalas should be constructed for the night stay of the devotees. The participation of traders in the annual fair should be ensured to give grandeur to the fair. In the light of the above-stated references or findings, it is proposed that the temple complex of Binsar Mahadev be included as the fifth Dham of Uttarakhand to promote tourism and boost the local economy.

References :

- Kala, R., Bhavsar, D., Kumar, A., Roy, A., & Rawat, L. (2018). Quantification of potential area of

incursion of pine in oak forest in western Himalaya using fuzzy classification technique. *Journal of Applied Remote Sensing*, 12.

- Cauhana, R. S. (n.d.). *Garhava* (Uttara-khanda) ke garha aur bharom ka itiha. Uttarakhand: Radhika Prakashana.
- Chauniyal, D. D., & Dutta, S. (2018). Application of topographic position index for classification of landforms in Dudhatoli Region of Garhwal Himalaya, Uttarakhand. *J. Indian Geomorphol*, 6, 28-41.
- Chavan, S. M. (2015). Mithuna: The Erotic Symbol of Divine Biunity with Reference to the Imagery of Shiva and Shakti in Indian Art. *PanEroticism*, 21-32.
- Goswami, P. K., & Pant, C. C. (2008). Morphotectonic evolution of the Binau-Ramganga-Naurar transverse valley, southern Kumaun Lesser Himalaya. *CURRENT SCIENCE*, 94, 1640-1645.
- Jayal, T. (2014). Evaluation of Drainage Morphometry in Thalishain Area of Lesser Himalaya: (Using Remote Sensing and GIS Techniques). *Landscape Ecology and Water Management, Springer*, 257-271.
- Jayal, T., & Chuniyal, D. (2015). Evolution Analysis Of Structures And Landforms Of Thalishain Area, Garhwal Himalaya, Uttarakhand. *International Journal of Recent Research in Interdisciplinary*

Sciences (IJRRIS), 2(2), 42-51.

- Jha, V. C. (1996). *Himalayan Geomorphology: Study of Himalayan Ramganga Basin*. Rawat Publication.
- Joshi, M. M. (2017). Almorea Janpad Ki Shakta Pratimayen. *Vidyawarta*.
- Maithani, V. (2004). *Garhwal Himalaya ki Dev Sansakriti: aik Samajik Adhyayan*. Gāndhī Hindustānī Sāhitya Sabhā.
- Metivier, K. (2016). Sounding Kirtan. *Religion and Movement*. Chicago: University of Chicago Divinity School Graduate Student Conference.
- Mishra, J., & Rout, S. (2020). Geopolymer Technology and Vastu Shastra for Environmental Protection: In the Context of Civil Engineering-Architecture Collaboration. *Journal of Advanced Research in Civil and Environmental Engineering*, 7, 1-5.
- Mittal, G. (2020). The state and the production of informalities in urban transport: Vikrams in Dehradun, India. *Geoforum*.
- Sengupta, N. (2019). Miscellaneous Other Uses. *Traditional Knowledge in Modern India*, 153-163.
- Sharma, C. M., Butola, D. S., Ghildiyal, S. K., & Gairola, S. (2013). Phytodiversity along an altitudinal gradient in Dudhatoli forest of Garhwal Himalaya, Uttarakhand, India. *International Journal of Medicinal and Aromatic Plants*, 3, 439-451.

